

Adapting Professional Language Competencies: Enhancing Foreign Language Training for Non- Linguistic University Graduates in Response to Modern Socio-Economic Changes and Global Cooperation

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Abstract:

Modern socio-economic changes in society associated with the updating of technologies, the growth of the flow of information, the rapid pace of knowledge acquisition and its use, the expansion and deepening of international cooperation, computerization and the creation of a new information industry, put forward new requirements for the professional training of a specialist and for his personal qualities that determine his professional characteristics and intellectual development. This provision is also true in relation to foreign language training of specialists, since practical proficiency in a foreign language is, in modern conditions, a mandatory prerequisite for the successful professional activity of a specialist - a graduate of a non-linguistic university.

Keywords: education, foreign languages, holistic approach, questionnaires, oral communication, written communication, speech competence, labor productivity, competence.

Introduction

In order to improve foreign language training of specialists, it is necessary to take into account changes related to production needs in relation to specialist qualifications and changes in training conditions. When considering the issue of new requirements in professional terms, it is advisable to proceed from the increasing need of society for specialists who speak a foreign language.

Numerous studies conducted in a non-linguistic university to determine the level of students' language proficiency, the author's observations of the learning process, and the results of tests confirm that a significant number of students fail to develop the skills and abilities at the level at which they could use a foreign language as a means of oral and written communication. Insufficient development of language and speech competence in the modern conditions of expanding international contacts is one of the significant factors in reducing labor productivity and limiting the specialist's ability to use a foreign language in his work.

The current program is based on the professional needs of specialists. Being standard, it cannot take into account the specific conditions of a particular type of university, which makes it necessary to solve this problem for university.

The lack of continuity between school and university and the low level of preparation of applicants must be taken into account when building a system of teaching foreign languages at a university. University teachers do not always succeed in solving the problem of leveling the foreign language training of students and bringing it to the level necessary for continuing education, including at a non-linguistic university, which requires a significant change in the beginning of work at the university on the language. No less significant is the restructuring of further teaching of foreign languages at the university. When adjusting the goals and objectives of teaching foreign languages, one should proceed from the requirements for the level of language training of a modern specialist, presented by social and economic changes in society and in production, respectively expressed by qualification characteristics.

The main objective of the study is to develop theoretical foundations of a foreign language course for students of a non-linguistic university aimed at developing the student's personality, satisfying both his personal needs and the requirements of modern scientific and technical production for a future specialist.

Methods

Research hypothesis. Building a training course based on a holistic approach, taking into account the relationship of all its parametric characteristics, will contribute to achieving the level of training of a technical specialist that meets modern requirements. It is advisable to distinguish between the stages of training taking into account the professional training of a specialist, as well as the required level of development of communicative competence, namely: a preparatory stage, a professionally oriented stage and a stage of special training with a certain ratio of the development of types of speech activity at each of them (preparatory stage - dominance of oral speech; professionally oriented stage - an increase in the role of reading with a significant weight of listening; stage of special training - the dominance of reading). It is further necessary to use intensive teaching methods (at the preparatory stage) and new organizational forms - lecture-practical, lecture and seminar classes (at the professionally oriented stage and the stage of special training).

In accordance with the subject of the study and the hypothesis, the following problems should be solved in the study: to identify theoretical provisions that can be the basis for a foreign language course; to justify the feasibility of changing the goals, content and technology of teaching in accordance with the requirements put forward for a graduate of a technical university; to prove the possibility and effectiveness of using new methodological approaches and organizational forms.

To solve these problems, the following tasks should be considered:

1. To determine modern requirements for the level of foreign language training of a specialist.
2. To clarify the goals and objectives of teaching foreign languages in a technical university in accordance with the modern needs of society imposed on technical specialists.

3. To establish the specifics of didactic and methodological principles of teaching students and to determine the specific provisions of the course being developed.
4. To justify the stages of training in accordance with modern requirements for training a specialist.
5. To justify a rational ratio of teaching various types of speech activity at each stage.
6. Clarify the principles of selection of language and text material by stages and conduct this selection.
7. Identify the specifics of using exercises taking into account each stage (types of exercises, the ratio of preparatory and speech exercises, their sequence, changing the system of exercises depending on the stage of training).
8. Determine the organizational forms of training.
9. Develop forms and methods for monitoring the effectiveness of the developed course.
10. Experimentally test the effectiveness of the developed course. In order to test the put forward hypothesis and solve the set tasks, along with studying domestic and foreign literature on didactics, psychology, linguistics, psycholinguistics and methods of teaching foreign languages, the following research methods were used: - analysis of intensive oral, communicative courses and intensive courses on teaching reading;
 1. observation of the pedagogical process of teaching foreign languages in a technical university;
 2. questionnaires (in order to identify students' opinions on the goals of teaching foreign languages in a non-linguistic university and their attitude towards foreign languages);
 3. conducting and analyzing tests (in order to determine the level of students' language proficiency and the development of skills and abilities that require adjustment and improvement by the beginning of their studies at the university and at certain stages of training);
 4. pilot work, including exploratory experiments of the preparatory stage and pilot training in order to test the effectiveness of the developed methodology.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the study. The expediency of a holistic approach to building a foreign language course in a non-linguistic university, which is implemented in the interconnected consideration of its main characteristics, is proven. The need to correct the goals and objectives of training in accordance with modern societal requirements for a technical specialist is substantiated. The theoretical foundations for building a course are identified.

The specificity of the manifestation of methodological and didactic principles of training is shown, and new methodological provisions are identified regarding the relationship between intensive and traditional teaching methods, the relationship between lectures and practical classes.

Results

The author substantiates the allocation of training stages taking into account the specifics of training in a technical university and the levels of formation of communicative competence, namely, the preparatory stage, professionally oriented and the stage of special training, and shows their specificity.

For the first time, when teaching foreign languages in a technical university, the ratio of all types of speech activity for each stage is determined.

The principles of selecting the content of training for each stage are clarified.

For the first time, the possibility of combining intensive and traditional methods within the preparatory stage in a technical university is proven. The possibility and effectiveness of using new

organizational forms of training - lecture-practical, lecture and seminar classes on individual special disciplines in English are substantiated.

Practical value. Based on the theoretical provisions, a version of the English language training course for future radio engineers in a technical university has been compiled, which can be used in whole or in part when teaching students of other specialties at a non-linguistic university, and the developed requirements can serve as a basis for preparing teaching aids for students of the radio engineering profile.

The developed theoretical provisions of the course can be used when adjusting programs, be a basis for developing courses on teaching other foreign languages for various specialties at a non-linguistic university, including universities of the humanities profile, as well as when developing courses for training referents-translators at a technical university.

Conclusion

In accordance with the chosen principles, the text material was selected and the content of the training was distributed into stages. A set of exercises for the development of all types of speech activity was compiled, a teaching methodology for the development of elementary communicative competence using intensive methods was created. Methodological recommendations for conducting various types of classes in English (lectures, lecture-practical and seminars) were developed.

1. The effectiveness of the course is ensured by the interrelation and interdependence of its characteristics, which are expressed by methodological categories. It is advisable to base the course on the connections between the levels of formation of communicative competence and the stages of training, which make up the course, between the learning objectives at each stage and the final requirements imposed on a technical specialist, between the choice of methods used and the degree of concentration of academic hours, between the form of classes (a combination of lectures and practical, lectures and seminars) and the level of development of the leading type of speech activity.
2. In accordance with the requirements put forward, it is advisable to divide the course of teaching a foreign language into three stages, determined by the specifics of training in a technical university and the levels of formation of communicative and professional competence, namely: the preparatory stage, the professionally oriented stage, the stage of special training.
3. For the effective implementation of the tasks of teaching a foreign language in the conditions of a non-linguistic technical university, the following ratio of speech activity types is required at each stage: at the preparatory stage, it is recommended to increase the specific weight and role of oral speech, due to the expediency of activating less developed skills to create a basis that ensures the transition to subsequent stages; at the professionally oriented stage and the stage of special training, the role of reading (as the main type of speech activity) and listening (as a source of information) increases, which is due to the specifics of a non-linguistic university and, accordingly, the professional needs of future engineers.
4. To create a uniform level of training for students at the preparatory stage, it is necessary to create a fundamentally new remedial preparatory course based on the use of elements of intensive methods, namely: the method of dynamic reading and the method of activating the capabilities of the individual and the team (G.A. Kitaygorodskaya).
5. For better development of oral speech skills and bringing the learning process closer to real conditions, it is recommended to use new organizational forms in the training course, such as lectures, lecture-practical and seminar classes on introduction to the specialty and one of the special subjects in English.

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